

Polar Front ecosystem studies using novel autonomous technologies: Knowledge for environmental management and assessing ecological risk (NFR # 326635)

The Barents Sea Polar Front as observed during cruises in (from left to right) August 2023, January 2024, and May 2022 (Photos: Frida Cnossen, Akvaplan-niva).

Project summary and objectives

Environmentally sustainable industry operations require comprehensive ecosystem understanding, safe and effective monitoring technologies, and a reliable data archive for assessing risk and driving management strategies. Perhaps nowhere is this more evident than in sensitive Arctic regions where the knowledge base is incomplete, operational risk is high, and databases are fragmented and not user-friendly. The PolarFront project conducted multi-seasonal, high-resolution studies of distribution, productivity and food-web dynamics across a wide size-spectrum of the pelagic community, from bacteria to whales. We worked in the Polar Front region of the Barents Sea, an area known to have disproportionately high ecological value and sensitivity, and one that marks the approximate southern boundary of the seasonal ice zone. We complemented shipboard sampling and experimental approaches with novel, integrated autonomous sampling technology to broaden the ecological context of point measurements, and to test the utility of these novel monitoring methods under challenging conditions, including the Polar Night. Since the Polar Front is known to act as a distributional boundary, an area of enhanced production, and an important feeding area for plankton, fish, seabirds and mammals, our ecological studies focused on these topics. We investigated the ecological foundation of the value of this region, with special attention to ecological processes and species of key ecosystem and management importance, including primary productivity, pelagic trophic pathways, krill, polar cod, and capelin, the latter two being important in the transfer of primary production to higher trophic level species. In our digitalization strategy we stressed conforming to national and international data management standards, as well as developing flexible solutions to format data for direct input into risk assessment, ecological, and management modelling systems. We spent considerable effort on communication of both data and scientific results to diverse users through scientific presentations and articles/blogs in the popular science press. Furthermore, more than 30 early career researchers took part in PolarFront research, including 11 whose projects were directly tied to our project. Close cooperation and active involvement of industry and management bodies throughout the project assured results were relevant and accessible to end-users.

Main objective: To evaluate the impact of the physical-chemical characteristics of the Polar Front on pelagic productivity and food-web dynamics to facilitate ecosystem-based management and mitigate potential risks of future petroleum development.

Secondary objectives:

- 1:** To **provide a coordinated set of sampling infrastructures** for optimal seasonally-resolved sampling.
- 2:** To characterise **spatio-temporal patterns in species distributions, size structure, and life-stages** of the pelagic community across the Polar Front.
- 3:** To quantify **spatio-temporal patterns in primary and secondary productivity** across the Polar Front.
- 4.** To **describe the trophic interactions** of the pelagic community across the Polar Front.
- 5:** To **compile, visualize, and archive high-resolution data sets** with applications for environmental risk assessment, regional management plans, scientific analyses, and public engagement.

Results

Use of a coordinated set of sampling infrastructures. We conducted **4 cruises of 8-12 days** each aboard the research vessel *Helmer Hanssen*. This ship is outfitted with the EK60 echosounder; an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP); a CTD/rosette with fluorescence, turbidity, and oxygen sensors; and a variety of standard sampling gear. In addition, we deployed both ship-based and autonomous sampling platforms, some of which carried new integrations of sensors. The Table below shows which sampling infrastructures were deployed during each cruise.

Use of such a wide range of sensors deployed from different platforms enabled us to sample/detect pelagic organisms and processes from the smallest size classes up to fish and whales, any simultaneously. **Such an array of infrastructures and marine technology has rarely been deployed in a single project** and during the cruises over multiple seasons.

Gear	May 2021	May 2022	Aug 2023	Jan 2024
SeaGlider with UVP-6 plankton imager and EK80 echosounder	X	X	X (2)	
SeaGlider with hydrophone	X	X		
Sailbuoy with ADCP	X	X		
Saibuoy with EK80 echosounder	X	X	X	
Otter unmanned surface vehicle with EK80 echosounder			X	

Moving Vessel Profiler: CTD, Laser optical plankton counter (LOPC)		X	X	X
Laser In Situ Scattering and Transmissometry (LISST)	X	X	X	X
Wide-band autonomous transceiver (WBAT)	X	X	X	X
LOPC + CTD		X	X	X

Phytoplankton biomass/fluorescence. Phytoplankton was studied on all cruises during the project, and unprecedentedly high concentrations of primary producers were found during May 2021 and 2022 across the Barents Sea Polar Front area. The diatom-dominated blooms were extending from deeply mixed Atlantic water with high nutrient levels into stratified Polar waters underneath sea ice that were already partly depleted of nutrients. **Depth-integrated chlorophyll *a* values were highest at the Front** and in the nutrient-rich Atlantic water further south (Fig. 1), whereas **highest concentrations of phytoplankton were found close to the surface in partly ice-covered waters. This important part of high spring production is not detectable by remote sensing and has probably been substantially underestimated** so far. In August, phytoplankton concentrations were much lower, and the species composition was very different from May, with dinoflagellates and coccolithophores being more dominant. Along the entire transect there was a layer of warm water in the upper 30-50 m (6-9°C), which was where almost all phytoplankton was found (Fig. 2). Despite low nutrient concentrations in this layer, the photosynthetic efficiency was as high as in spring, indicating a well-adapted community.

Fig. 1: Depth-integrated chlorophyll *a* measured during the spring bloom in May 2021 and 2022.

Fig. 2: Distribution of chlorophyll a (in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) during the August cruise – a result of strong thermal stratification of the water column. The surface zone of the Polar Front was difficult to identify based on temperature and salinity in August but was most likely around Station 8.

Phytoplankton physiology. A vertically profiling fast repetition rate fluorometer (FRRF) was deployed during the Polar Front expedition in all seasons, providing **novel insights into the *in-situ* photosynthetic yield under ambient irradiance**. There were clear seasonal and vertical gradients in the estimated yield and the estimated chlorophyll a (based also on algal fluorescence). In spring and summer (Fig. 3), vertical gradients in the photosynthetic yield were related to ambient irradiance with increases towards depth primarily due to photochemical and non-photochemical quenching. Maximum yields were reached typically at depths of 20-40m which often coincided with maximum chlorophyll a concentrations in the stratified water layers. One surprising result was that **large net phytoplankton collected in mid-winter had high yields above 0.5 and highest values at the most Arctic stations**. This indicates that these phytoplankton cells (dominated by dinoflagellates at that time) had a high potential to use light as soon as it would become available in spring for photosynthesis.

Fig. 3: Typical examples of photosynthetic yield and chlorophyll a concentrations in the uppermost 80-90m of the water column for spring, summer and winter in the Polar Front region, determined with an *in-situ* FRRF profiler.

Mesozooplankton community and *Calanus* lipid content. Mesozooplankton data from **May 2021 and 2022 revealed low overall abundance, particularly south of the Front**, while Arctic waters showed higher abundance and biomass in May 2022 due to larger Arctic *Calanus* species. Samples from August 2023 and January 2024 are under analysis. Preliminary results from August 2023 indicate a dominance of small copepods and benthic larvae in the upper water column. The occurrence of species typical of coastal Norwegian Sea waters suggests high degree of advection of water masses from the Norwegian Sea. In all seasons, *Calanus* within the size range of the boreal species *C. finmarchicus* dominated on the southern side of the Front, while the Arctic *C. glacialis* prevailed north of the Front and in ice-covered areas. *Metridia longa*, a copepod of similar size, contributed substantially, particularly in January. In May, Arctic *Calanus* north of the front had a new generation, while boreal populations south of the front were only beginning reproduction. By August, southern and northern populations were in overwintering stages, while central populations showed delayed or secondary reproduction. January populations were dominated by overwintering stages, with mating observed in *C. glacialis*.

Lipid content in *Calanus* was lowest in May and in combination with overall low abundance this resulted in an overall low population lipid content in the study area, with the highest values north of the front. Although individual *Calanus* had relatively low lipid levels in August, the higher abundance compared to May resulted in an overall increase in population lipid content in the study area. Also in August, highest lipid content was observed in the north. **The Arctic area north of the Front thus appears to be better feeding ground for herbivore predators during the productive season.** In January, total lipid content was similar to that in August, with higher values observed at depth in the north and in surface layers in the south.

Fig. 4: Seasonal and spatial variability in population lipid content of *Calanus* spp. across the study area. In August and January, lipid content was estimated for the population at depth (“deep”, upper 100 m over the sea floor) and in surface waters (“surface”, upper 50 m). In May, lipid content was estimated for *Calanus* sampled from the entire water column. Shaded area indicates areas ice covered during sampling.

Pelagic secondary production during a mismatch scenario. Oceanic fronts world-wide have been suggested to be both conservation hotspots and hotspots for ecosystem services. During the Polar Front project, a mismatch between primary production and secondary production was observed in the region of the Polar Front in May 2021 and 2022. Here, we analysed secondary production in 2022 with high spatial resolution along two transects across the front during the same time period. By combining egg production measurements at stations with counts of females across the entire transects, we calculated that *Calanus* egg production amounted to ca. 10 % of the total production of larger mesozooplankton with similar or higher egg production in polar waters than in Atlantic Water. **The zone of the surface expression of the Polar Front (ca 75.75° N) emerged as a region of elevated production**, with both increased production of larger mesozooplankton and *Calanus* egg production in this region. This important role of the surface Front was not evident from earlier, station-based sampling.

Extreme mismatch during spring blooms. Our recent paper (Renaud, Daase et al. 2024) describes extreme mismatch situations during spring 2021 and 2022 based on our cruises. **Unprecedentedly high phytoplankton biomass values were encountered, likely accumulated due to the lack of efficient grazing (top-down control), as large herbivorous zooplankton were found in very low densities** in both years. Capelin collected in Atlantic Water in 2022 had very low stomach fullness, reflecting the lack of food, although north of the Front capelin were feeding much better. The lack of abundant large grazing zooplankton continued at least until the end of June in both years, documented by

echosounders on Sailbuoy platforms that we had in the region for 2 months. The fate of the produced biomass is unclear, and earlier spring blooms in the Barents Sea might exacerbate the **low pelagic trophic transfer efficiency due to a temporal mismatch** of seasonal phytoplankton and zooplankton development.

Fig. 5: Stomach fullness and composition of capelin (**S**mall, **M**edium, and **L**arge size classes) and polar cod at different stations in 2022. Station M22_S2* is the only station north of the Polar Front where trawling is typically not possible due to ice cover. Capelin here were found in deeper Atlantic Water layers.

Documenting brine rejection at the Polar Front. Brine formation is a rapid process and is rarely observed in the field. During the January 2024 cruise **we were fortunate to witness vertical processes in the water column during ice formation at the Polar Front** in a region of new ice formation. Here, we observed extremely high salinities (> 35.2 psu) in surface waters. At the same time, we observed increased densities of small particles (between ca. 1 and 300 μm ESD in size) at surface and throughout the water column (to 250 m). Increased particle densities were observed also further north along the sampled transect (Fig. 6). We interpret this as locations where ice formation recently took place, and where the rapid brine release led to increased particle flux.

Fig. 6: Transect across the Polar Front, Barents Sea, ca. 29.5 °E. Top: Salinity [psu]. Bottom: LISST data [log (biovolume concentration)].

Seasonal particle distribution. The Polar Front plays different roles for particles/aggregations in different seasons. In spring it was an area of accumulation, with higher concentrations at the frontal zone (green bars) compared to stations in Atlantic (red bars) or Arctic domains (blue bars) (Fig. 7). During winter, the Polar Front separated Arctic waters that were full of large particles (right of plot, yellows, greens and red) and plankton from Atlantic waters low in particles (blue area south (left) of 76.5°N) (Fig. 6, bottom panel).

Fig. 7: Depth-integrated numbers of particles ($\times 10^8$) at stations along the study transect in May 2022. Green bars (highest values) occur largely in the frontal zone (75.5 – 76.8°N).

Fish and Macrozooplankton Distribution and Diversity. From the start of the transect to ca. 75.75°N in May 2022, large and dense schools of capelin were observed between 50 m and 100 m. North of 75.75° N, where water thermal stratification and the Front began, peak fish biomass (mostly capelin) was deeper and centered around 100 m, still in Atlantic Water (Fig. 8a, white). A strong acoustic signal from the 120 kHz transducer, likely from abundant small larval fishes and crustacean macrozooplankton (e.g. krill), was observed between 50 m to 100 m at latitudes north of 75.75° N, and then north of 76.8° N, where the entire water column was dominated by polar waters (Figure 8a, blue). In August 2023, most pelagic fish and macrozooplankton biomass were concentrated below 200 m (Figure 8b, white and blue). In January 2024, swim bladdered fish with a strong signal at 18kHz and 38kHz dominated the water column between 50 m and 200 m south of 77° N (Figure 8c, red and yellow). Fish species with a strong signal at all three frequencies, likely capelin, with the

addition of crustacean macrozooplankton dominated the signal below 200 m, and then closer to the surface north of 77° N (Figure 8c, white band).

Fig. 8: RGB echograms from the hull-mounted EK60 echosounder across the Polar Front in (a) May 2022, (b) August 2023, and (c) January 2024. Due to the unique frequency response of each species, the visualized signal at each frequency is associated with the presence of a different group of organisms (18kHz and 38kHz: swim bladder fishes, 120kHz: small larval fishes and crustacean zooplankton).

Mesocosm calibration of echosounder targets. The northern shrimp (*Pandalus borealis*) fishery, an important commercial fishery in the Barents Sea, is prone to bycatch of polar

cod (*Boreogadus saida*), a key Arctic forage fish species. Furthermore, northern shrimp and polar cod spatial distributions increasingly coincide with that of Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*). Discrimination between the acoustic signals of Atlantic cod, polar cod and northern shrimp could provide more information on the risk of polar cod bycatch in the northern shrimp fishery in addition to improving the accuracy of non-lethal stock assessment surveys. We conducted a series of single-species mesocosm experiments for broadband target strength spectra measurements of Atlantic cod, polar cod and northern shrimp to assess the potential for acoustic spectral-based species discrimination.

Hundreds of target strength spectra (TS(f)) were extracted from the broadband target strength spectra measurements (Figure 9D-I) for each species and used to train machine-learning classification algorithms (i.e. classifiers). **We found that two supervised learning classifiers, LightGBM and support vector machine, were able to achieve high classification performance (89%) with a single 200 kHz transducer operating in broadband mode.** These promising results indicate the possibility to use mesocosm-trained acoustic classifiers to overcome challenges in fisheries in the Barents Sea, such as quantifying bycatch risk.

Fig. 9: Examples of the target spectra of each selected detection from an individual track of each species using multiplexing broadband echosounders. D-F) Echograms of a selected isolated track from Atlantic cod, polar cod, and shrimp, respectively. Measured target spectra of the selected tracks; G) Atlantic cod with 19 detections in the 94-158 kHz bandwidth and 13 detections in the 189-249 kHz bandwidth (grey lines), H) polar cod track with 6 in the 94-158 kHz bandwidth and 4 target spectra in the 189-249 kHz bandwidth, I) northern shrimp track with 9 target spectra in the 94-158 kHz bandwidth and 10 target spectra in the 189-249 kHz bandwidth.

Data sets. As of 16 January 2025 **we have published 64 data sets** from the project (using our Zenodo community platform: <https://zenodo.org/communities/polarfront/about>). Each has a doi and a list is provided as Appendix 1 to this report. We did not enter the datasets into CRISTIN due to the uncertainties over the past several years regarding its longevity, and whether all information would be transferred to the new platform. It seemed an extraordinary effort solely for the production of this final report to enter them manually in the on-line reporting form. The Zenodo platform also contains cruise reports (included as non-peer-reviewed publications in the on-line reporting forms) and presentations during the project.

Implementation and use of resources

In addition to the substantial funding from the RCN and the two industry partners in the project (Equinor, ConocoPhillips), we benefited from strong collaboration and financial support from the ARCTOS Research network, the NFR projects *Nansen Legacy* and *Deep Impact*, and the EU project *BioGlider*. The May 2021 cruise, which took place before the start of the main project, received significant funding from Equinor. Partner institutions, especially UiT The Arctic University of Norway, provided substantial in-kind support for both ship time (UiT) and subsidizing researcher time and technology infrastructure.

Dissemination

Popular science outreach. Throughout the project, partners produced news stories and distributed them on their communications platforms. Popular lectures on the project were given by one researcher in Germany. Fourteen cruise blogs, including one distributed via Forskning.no were produced on a wide range of topics. See the electronic report documents for details. A video based on the August 2023 cruise is in the final stages of editing by a professional filmmaker in Scotland. This will be available on his YouTube channel/web site early in 2025.

Scientific presentations. A number of presentations at international conferences on polar science, marine ecology, and marine technology were delivered. See the electronic report documents for details.

Manuscripts in review/preparation. Two articles have been published on project work, including one on the extraordinarily high levels of chlorophyll biomass and the documentation and consequences of extreme mismatch between microalgae and zooplankton grazers. We continue work on (at least) 16 manuscripts that are expected to be published within the next 2 years from the Project (see table below). One of these was submitted in November 2024 and we await reviewer comments. Three others are expected to be submitted by the end of March 2025. The volume of biological and sensor data collected necessitates significant processing in the lab. Further, some work will be

produced as part of MS and PhD theses to be completed. The ship issues that led to moving our January cruise from 2023 to 2024 also resulted in a delay of processing samples and data.

Table indicating title/ theme of planned PolarFront papers to be submitted, the main author(s), and the projected submission date.

First/key author(s)	Short descriptive title	Status/planned submission date
Daase et al	Seasonal variability in zooplankton across the Barents Sea Polar Front	Oct-25
Sandbank et al	Fish and macrozooplankton assemblages across the Polar Front	Jan-25
Sandbank et al	Vertical distributions of pelagic species using an acoustic probe	Mar-25
Sandbank, Cnossen et al	Seasonal changes in capelin diet in the western Barents Sea	Sep-25
Sandbank et al	Barents Sea isoscapes	Feb-26
Gradinger et al	Seasonal variability in phytoplankton community composition	
Gradinger et al	Vertically resolving estimation of Arctic phytoplankton physiological variables	
Leu, Campbell, et al	Seasonal changes in primary productivity and photophysiology	Oct-25
Miettinen, Campbell et al	Dynamics of microbial activity across the Barents Sea Polar Front	

Basedow, Granaas, Daase et al.	Egg production as a proportion of zooplankton production	Jan-25
Basedow, de la Guardia et al.	Aggregation and production of zooplankton at the Polar Front	July-25
Basedow, Trudnowska et al	Role of marine snow in the food web of the western Barents Sea	
Geoffroy, Basedow et al	Spectral size distribution and segregation	
Basedow et al	Brine rejection speeds vertical particle flux at the ice edge	
Dunn et al	Broadband acoustic classification of Atlantic cod, polar cod, and northern shrimp in mesocosm experiments	Submitted Nov.12 2024
Gradinger et al.	Winter phytoplankton composition and activity	May-25

Contributions to early career scientists

Such a diverse project with 4 oceanographic cruises afforded many opportunities for participation by early career researchers (ECRs) (Table below). For **eleven ECRs**, including bachelor, MS, PhD, and postdoctoral researchers PolarFront provided **a major portion or all of the data and context for their projects. Ten other ECRs** used the PolarFront platforms to collect data for their research topics not specifically related to the objectives of the PolarFront project. **Eleven ECRs** used cruise opportunities to gain experience at sea and learn about the project; on-board they contributed to sampling for the project and writing of blogs and cruise reports. It is clear that this project contributed greatly to training of **these 32 ECRs from 11 Norwegian and international institutions**. We see this is a highly valuable output of the project and are quite proud of our work toward providing these opportunities.

*Table listing early career researcher (ECR) participation in the four project cruises. Number in parentheses following name indicates number of PolarFront cruises in which the ECR participated. Name in **bold text***

indicates PolarFront cruises contributed substantially to ECR projects. Value to ECR indicates whether the main point was to gain experience, to assist with sampling, or to sample specifically for their ECR work.

Name	ECR status	Institution	Value to ECR
Alun Jones	Post-doc	NTNU	experience
Jessie Gardner	Post-doc	UiT	sampling
Laurene Pecuchet	Post-doc	UiT	sampling
Muhammed Asim	PhD Candidate	UiT	experience
Johanne Skrefsrud	PhD Candidate	UiB	experience
Jakob Dörr	PhD Candidate	UiB	experience
Muriel Dunn	PhD Candidate	Akvaplan-niva	sampling for PhD
Mads Schultz	PhD Candidate	Nord University	experience
Apollo Lizano	PhD Candidate	Nord University	experience
Estelle Coguiec	PhD Candidate	UiT	sampling
Hao Chen	PhD Candidate	UiT	experience
Svenja Neumann	Post-MS	UiT	experience
Nellie Wullenweber	MS student	Met Institute	experience
Evelyn Strombom	PhD candidate	Univ Minnesota	experience
Anna Miettinen (3)	MS student/tech	UiT/Akvaplan-niva	sampling
Torkel Granaas	MS student	UiT	sampling for MS
Megan Lenss	MS student	UiT	sampling
Joel Wernström	PhD candidate	UiT	sampling
Nicolas Gosset (2)	PhD candidate	UiT	sampling for PhD
Luc Hallali	PhD student	UiT	sampling
Einat Sandbank (3)	PhD student	Memorial Univ.	sampling for PhD
Fabio Viotti	MS student	UiT	sampling
Frida Cnossen (3)	MS student/tech	Akvaplan-niva/Univ Cote d'Azur	sampling for MS

Meghan Lightfoot	MS student	Univ Delaware	sampling for MS
Emma Forss	MS student	UiT	sampling
Victoria Eggen	MS student	UiT	experience
Lars Ursem	MS student	Akvaplan-niva	experience
Florence Rappin	MS student	UiT	Sampling for MS
Lorenz Schick	MS student	UiT	Sampling for MS
Kelsey Rae Hanson	MS student	UiT	sampling
Sophie Albertsen	MS student	UiO	sampling for MS
Mathieu Lutier	Post-doc	UiO	Sampling for project
Irene Milagros Solchaga	BSc student	UiT	sampling for BSc

Appendix 1. List of published datasets with doi from the PolarFront project as of 16 January 2025. Note: due to large file sizes, some the of EK80 echosounder datasets were published as multiple files, each with its own doi.

1. Split-beam echosounder data from keel-mounted EK60 during PolarFront 2024-01 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14224617>
2. Wideband acoustic transceiver data from probe attached to Frankenstein rosette during PolarFront 2024-01 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223590>
3. LOPC (laser optical plankton counter) data captured during PolarFront 2024-01 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223504>
4. Ship logs from Helmer Hanssen on PolarFront cruise 2024-01. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223391>
5. Hydrography from LOPC-attached CTD during PolarFront cruise 2024-01. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223360>
6. Hydrography profiles from ship CTD captured during PolarFront cruise 2024-01. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223310>
7. EK80 from PolarFront seaglider SG644 2023-08-18/2023-08-25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946035>
8. Physical oceanography captured by PolarFront Seaglider SG644 in 2023-08. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13947022>
9. Split-beam echosounder data from keel-mounted EK60 during PolarFront 2023-08 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10057304>
10. PolarFront cruise 2023-08 ship logs from Helmer Hanssen. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054152>
11. Vertical hydrography profiles from CTD rosette downcasts during PolarFront cruise 2023-08. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10044202>
12. UVP6 from PolarFront seaglider SG644 2023-08-18/2023-08-25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10041064>
13. Sailbuoy Echo PolarFront EK80 echosounder data [5/5] 2023-09-15 to 2023-09-22. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10036829>
14. Sailbuoy Echo PolarFront EK80 echosounder data [4/5] 2023-09-04 to 2023-09-14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10036827>
15. Sailbuoy Echo PolarFront EK80 echosounder data [3/5] 2023-08-27 to 2023-09-03. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10036825>
16. Sailbuoy Echo PolarFront EK80 echosounder data [2/5] 2023-08-24 to 2023-08-26. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10036823>
17. Sailbuoy Echo PolarFront EK80 echosounder data [1/5] 2023-08-18 to 2023-08-23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10036821>
18. Sailbuoy Echo PolarFront EK80 echosounder datasets 2023-08 to 2023-09. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10035461>
19. LOPC (Laser Optical Plankton Counter) data from Frankenstein rosette profiles during PolarFront 2023-08. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652773>
20. Moving vessel profiler (MVP) transect from PolarFront 2023-08 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10363061>

21. Raw EK80 echosounder data of northern shrimp collected by wideband autonomous transceiver in mesocosm AZKABAN 2023-01-26.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289764>
22. Raw EK80 echosounder data of polar cod collected by wideband autonomous transceiver in mesocosm AZKABAN 2023-01-19 and 24.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289738>
23. Raw EK80 echosounder data of Atlantic cod collected by wideband autonomous transceiver in mesocosm AZKABAN 2023-01-20.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289718>
24. Calibration dataset for WBAT (SN253120). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289670>
25. CTD and EK80 from PolarFront surface vehicle Otter Otto 2023-08.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14651155>
26. LOPC (Laser Optical Plankton Counter) data from a 333 km MVP transect during PolarFront cruise 2023-08. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652831>
27. Wideband acoustic transceiver data from probe attached to Frankenstein rosette during PolarFront 2023-08 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512950>
28. Macrozooplankton at the Barents Sea Polar Front in May 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7763682>
29. Pelagic Fish at the Barents Sea Polar Front in May 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7755814>
30. LISST particle sizes from 11 vertical profiles taken during PolarFront cruise 2022-05.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513025>
31. LOPC (Laser Optical Plankton Counter) data from two MVP transects taken during PolarFront cruise 2022-05. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7473507>
32. LOPC (Laser Optical Plankton Counter) data from Frankenstein rosette profiles during PolarFront 2022-05 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7473511>
33. Split-beam echosounder data from keel-mounted EK60 during PolarFront 2022-05 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7473204>
34. Seawater velocities from ship acoustic Doppler current profiler during PolarFront 2022-05 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7473157>
35. Ship logs from Helmer Hanssen on PolarFront cruise 2022-05.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7473028>
36. Vertical hydrography profiles from CTD rosette downcasts during PolarFront cruise 2022-05. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418734>
37. Wideband acoustic transceiver data from probe attached to rosette on PolarFront 2022-05 cruise. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418828>
38. Sailbuoy Echo sensor data logs from PolarFront campaign 2022-04-29 to 2022-05-13.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14617356>
39. Seawater velocities and sensor data from Sailbuoy ADCP on campaign the PolarFront project in 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609143>
40. Moving vessel profiler (MVP) transects from PolarFront 2022-05 cruise.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10363774>
41. EK80, UVP6, and oceanography from PolarFront seaglider SG644 deployed 2022-05-19/2022-05-26. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14644121>

42. Hydrophone recordings and oceanography from PolarFront Seaglider SG153 deployed 2022-05-19. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14643731>
43. Sailbuoy Iskant EK80 echograms and data logs from PolarFront campaign 2022-05-19/2022-07-24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14638167>
44. Sailbuoy Echo EK80 raw echograms captured on campaign for PolarFront 2022-04-29 to 2022-05-13. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14617117>
45. Seawater velocities measured from autonomous sailbuoy ADCP in the Barents Sea from May to July 2021 on campaign the PolarFront project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7463097>
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